

Kinetics and Mechanism of Photodecomposition of Nifedipine by Use of Quantitative Glc Method

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NIFEDIPINE i.e. dimethyl-1,4-dihydro-2,6-dimethyl-4-(2-nitrophenyl)-3,5-pyridine dicarboxylate (1) belongs to a class of drugs having calcium antagonist activity¹.

The drug is reported to be highly light-sensitive, and there exists a controversy regarding its degradation products and the extent of degradation under different light conditions particularly in solution²⁻⁷. A detailed study was therefore undertaken to investigate the extent and mechanism of photolytic degradation in solution and in solid form.

In this paper, we are reporting the extent and mechanism of degradation as a function of concentration, light intensity and irradiation time under different light conditions, in solution. The stability was tested by using sodium benzoate as stabiliser. The degradation in solid form was also studied under different light conditions. The mechanistic route for degradation of bulk drug and in solution was suggested from the study.

Experimental

Nifedipine (USP) reference standard was obtained from Ana Laboratories (India). Sodium benzoate (A.R.) and chloroform (AnalaR) were used. The modified glc method was utilised in the study². A Perkin-Elmer 900 instrument was used: glass column (2 m × 2 mm id) packed with 3% OV1 on

Gas Chrom Q (100–120 mesh), oven temperature = 180°, the injector port and detector temperature = 275°, flow rate of nitrogen = 40 ml min⁻¹, flow rate of hydrogen and air used for the detector flame = 200 ml min⁻¹.

Photodecomposition study: Solutions of **1** in chloroform of 10, 1, 0.1 and 0.05 mg ml⁻¹ concentrations were prepared, and were exposed to artificial mercury light (400–650 nm) and the degradation was studied at intervals of 1 h by glc method. The extent of degradation under light of various intensities on nifedipine was studied by exposing solutions of 1.0 mg ml⁻¹ concentration in chloroform (in 25 ml flask) and a bulk drug (in petri dish) to day light, mercury light, lamp light (100 W), sunlight, uv light (190–350 nm) and visible light (350–600 nm). The degradation was monitored at intervals of 1 h by glc technique. The nifedipine bulk drug exposed to artificial light conditions was investigated after every 12 h. The stability of the drug was studied by addition of sodium benzoate with 10⁻⁶, 10⁻⁴, 10⁻²M strength in solutions of **1** (0.1 mg ml⁻¹ in methanol) and the solutions were exposed to visible light. The degradation was monitored at intervals of 1 h by glc method.

Results and Discussion

Typical chromatogram of nifedipine with the degradation products **2** and **3** reveal sharp and well-separated peaks with good resolution and no interference from each other. Due to the rapidity and specificity of the method, it was used to study the photodegradation in bulk drug and in solution.

Photolytic degradation in solution:

Concentration effect: The solution of 10 mg ml⁻¹ concentration shows only 4.0% degradation when exposed to mercury light for 8 h, a slow degradation in agreement with Squella *et al.*⁵, while the solutions of 0.1 and 0.01 mg ml⁻¹ concentrations show 35 and 55% decomposition respectively, at same roomlight conditions, a fast degradation as reported by other workers^{4,6,7}. Thus, the study indicates that nifedipine in solution at lower concentration (< 0.1 mg ml⁻¹) is more susceptible to photodegradation. The formation of **2** was observed as only a photolytic degradation product.

Different light conditions: The solutions of **1** at 1.0 mg ml⁻¹ concentration in chloroform were exposed to different light conditions, and the extent of degradation was studied at different time intervals. The solution exposed to uv light showed only 6–7% degradation even after 8 h with the formation of **2** as a degradation product, which is in agreement with that reported by Ebel *et al.*⁴. The solution of **1** exposed to sunlight shows 100% quantitative degradation within an hour and only **2** was observed as an exclusive degradation product. In visible light, it shows 100% decomposition within 8 h with only **2** as the degradation product. However, under artificial mercury light, it shows 12.5% degradation

after 8 h and 100% decomposition on the 5th day. At room light condition, the degradation was observed to be very slow, as reported by Squella *et al.*⁵, showing only 4.5% degradation after 8 h and 100% decomposition on the 14th day. However, a mixture of **2** (94%) and **3** (6%) was observed after 100% degradation on the 14th day under roomlight condition. The same solution kept for a further one month showed 88% of **2** and 12% of **3**. Thus slow degradation follows the initial photolytic degradation to yield product **2** followed by slow oxidation of **2** to product **3**. In order to confirm the oxidation of **2** to **3**, a solution of **1** after exposure to visible light for 12 h (to insure 100% conversion into **2**) was kept for one month without any artificial light and was found to have converted 12% into **3**. Further, it was confirmed by converting nifedipine into **3** by the procedure of Jacobson *et al.*² and thus comparing the relative retention time with that of the decomposed product. Therefore, the mechanistic route can be given as

The photolytic degradation was studied by adding sodium benzoate as a stabiliser to quench photolytic degradation at different concentrations ranging from 10⁻² to 10⁻⁶M in solution of **1** in methanol. The study shows that the stabilisation was improved almost 50% with addition of 10⁻⁶M sodium benzoate into 0.1 mg ml⁻¹ solution of nifedipine. Thus, the stability of **1** can be improved by using quenching reagents.

Photolytic degradation in bulk drug:

The photolytic degradation of nifedipine bulk drug is slow compared to the solution form, but with significant degradation. The nifedipine solid when exposed to sunlight showed 100% photodecomposition within 6 h. However, it showed a different degradation pathway than that in solution form. The formation of both **2** (86%) and **3** (14%) as degradation products was observed under sunlight. The formation of **3** was faster at the initial period and attained equilibrium after 2–3 h while formation of **2** was linear following first order kinetics. Therefore, the degradation in bulk drug can be presented as

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Under artificial mercury light condition, it showed only 3% conversion after 24 h with a half-life of 58 days. In visible light, however, the drug was completely decomposed within 30 h with formation of **2** as the major product. The bulk drug, even in uv light, showed formation of **2** as a major degradation product as reported by Ebel *et al.*⁴ with a half-life of 32 days.

The study thus concludes that the greater stability of nifedipine in solution at higher concentration can be explained by intermolecular hydrogen bonding. The degradation can be retarded by the use of quenching reagent as a stabiliser. The degradation route in solution and solid forms were observed to be different. The bulk drug showed both **2** and **3** as photolytic products, while **2** is the only photolytic product in solution and **3** being an oxidative product developed from **2**.

The results are useful in preformulation studies for optimal design of dosage for solid and in solutions and will provide a stability indicative procedure for pharmaceutical analysis.

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